

TikTok Trends and Teachers' Hijab Styles: Social Reflections from the Perspective of Islamic Religious Education at Muhammadiyah 1 Vocational School, Kepanjen

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Abstract:

The development of the digital world has an impact on changing perspectives and ways of dressing. This study aims to examine the style and model of veiling or hijab of female teachers at SMK Muhammadiyah 1 Kepanjen which is inspired by hijab tutorial content on TikTok in the perspective of Islamic religious education. This study uses a descriptive qualitative approach with a phenomenological research type that aims to understand and know the experiences of female teachers at SMK Muhammadiyah 1 Kepanjen in following the hijab trend on TikTok. The researcher took five female teachers as research subjects with data collection techniques through interviews, non-participatory observation, and content analysis. The results of the study show that the hijab trend on TikTok has a positive impact on teachers to appear confident, relevant to students, fashionable and polite hijab, friendly expressions because of the hijab, and the relationship with Islamic religious education. The values of Islamic religious education such as *uswatun hasanah*, *tawasuth*, and noble character. Hijab trends shouldn't be avoided as long as they don't abandon Islamic values. They can be a learning tool, a visual means of preaching, and a role model in the school environment.

Keywords— *hijab trend; Tik Tok Hijab Tutorials; Islamic religious education*

I. INTRODUCTION

The development of the digital world has had an impact on changing perspectives and ways of dressing [1]. Women's clothing trends are now increasingly diverse depending on what they watch on social media, impacting their expression of identity and clothing style [3]. One social media platform that has had an impact on changing clothing trends is the TikTok platform. TikTok is currently the most popular social media application due to the wide range of content available, from entertainment and education to fashion inspiration, that is easily accessible to its users [5]. Female teachers are role models. role models for students, especially girls, because they always imitate how their teachers dress.

Based on the results of our initial observations at Muhammadiyah 1 Kepanjen Vocational School, we found several female teachers with various headscarf styles, ranging from square *ceruti* models to *pashmina*. *Ceruti*, and regular square Paris with additional accessories. The hijab style was obtained from the hijab tutorial content they followed on TikTok [3, 9]. Female teachers at SMK Muhammadiyah 1 Kepanjen make the hijab style not only as a symbol of religiosity but also as a self-expression, aesthetics, and existence in the public space. The phenomenon of the hijab trend on TikTok adapted by female teachers of SMK Muhammadiyah 1 Kepanjen is interesting to be studied reflectively. In the context of Islamic religious education, the hijab style of female teachers is a role model in the school environment, so the role of female teachers is not only educating verbally, but also through their appearance and behavior [14, 15].

As an Islamic-based educational institution, SMK Muhammadiyah 1 Kepanjen also focuses on instilling Islamic values as an important part of the school's culture. The emergence of the hijab style trend on TikTok has provided a wide variety of hijab styles and models that have become popular among female teachers [3, 7]. Sometimes there are some hijab styles that do not reflect Islamic identity, because they want to appear different, more confident, attractive, and more relevant to the eyes of students [1, 10]. This is considered an effort to adapt to current developments and feel closer to students because they are active social media users [3, 7].

Several previous studies have shown that the impact of social media can change the mindset, clothing style, and behavior of both young and adult generations [1, 3]. Currently, wearing the hijab is not only a symbol of religious values, but also a lifestyle influenced by celebrity hijabers, content creators, and popular trends on social media [1, 7]. In the context of Islamic religious education, the hijab style of female teachers must continue to comply with Islamic law. In Surah An-Nur verse 31, it is explained that the concept of wearing the hijab or veil must cover the *aurat*, reflecting modesty, simplicity, and the intention of worship [10, 12].

Based on the explanation above, this study answers the following main questions: (1) What are the forms of expression and female teachers in wearing the hijab at SMK Muhammadiyah 1 Kepanjen? (2) How does the TikTok trend influence the hijab style of female teachers at SMK Muhammadiyah 1 Kepanjen?

This study aims to: (1) describe the forms of female teachers' expressions in wearing the hijab at Muhammadiyah 1 Vocational School, Kepanjen. (2) describe the influence of

TikTok trends on the hijab styles of female teachers at Muhammadiyah 1 Vocational School, Kepanjen.

This study uses a descriptive qualitative approach by applying the IMRAD method (Introduction, Method, Result, and Discussion) [11]. This study seeks to highlight the trend of female teachers wearing the hijab at SMK Muhammadiyah 1 Kepanjen, inspired by content on TikTok as a form of expression from a contextual, adaptive, and aesthetic perspective on Islamic religious education. It is hoped that it will provide a complete and in-depth understanding for female teachers regarding the dynamics of the hijab trend on social media, as well as its implications for the world of Islamic education today.

II. RESEARCH METHODS

This study uses a descriptive qualitative approach with a phenomenological research type that aims to understand and understand the experiences of female teachers at Muhammadiyah 1 Kepanjen Vocational School in following the hijab trend on TikTok [4, 16]. The researcher chose SMK Muhammadiyah 1 Kepanjen, an Islamic-based vocational high school under the auspices of the Muhammadiyah association. Based on the results of initial observations conducted periodically, which showed the phenomenon of the hijab style of female teachers inspired by hijab tutorial content on TikTok. The researcher took five female teachers as research subjects who were specifically selected to ensure the focus of the research on the expression, motivation, and shape of the hijab of female teachers inspired by hijab tutorial content on TikTok [16].

Data collection was obtained through semi-structured interviews, by asking questions about motivation in choosing a hijab model or style, and their impressions and feelings about hijab trends on TikTok [4]. Non-participatory observation, observations were conducted over a period of seven days by observing the teacher's hijab style, both while teaching and when interacting with students and colleagues [6]. Furthermore, TikTok content analysis, a search for TikTok content followed by informants as a reference and inspiration for choosing a hijab style [6]. The data analysis technique in this study refers to the interactive model of Miles, Huberman and Saldana, namely data condensation, data presentation, and drawing conclusions. This approach allows researchers to manage data systematically and reflectively [8].

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Hijab Trends Make You Confident

The various hijab styles and models adopted by female teachers at SMK Muhammadiyah 1 Kepanjen have an impact on self-confidence during activities. The selection of hijab styles and models adopted from TikTok trends adapts to facial shapes [1, 15]. Several hijab tutorial content that was followed and implemented while in the school environment actually reaped positive praise from the school community. The praise received increased self-confidence during activities both outside and inside the classroom [2, 13]. The hijab trend phenomenon that is widely followed by female teachers at SMK Muhammadiyah 1 Kepanjen must remain within the realm of neatness and politeness. SMK Muhammadiyah 1

Kepanjen is an Islamic school that implements Islamic culture, so the style of dress must remain sharia. Islam teaches a style of dress that is polite and covers the aurat so as not to arouse lust for the opposite sex. Contemporary hijab styles can boost self-confidence and increase enthusiasm for activities [1, 2]. Assessment from peers and students is a form of appreciation and recognition that strengthens self-confidence [13, 14].

B. Friendly Expression because of Hijab

The appearance of female teachers who follow the hijab trend on TikTok depicts a friendly and confident expression in the school environment. A friendly expression is a tool for building social relationships through positive nonverbal communication and can increase social attraction [2, 9]. Female teachers always appear with a friendly and smiling face in the school environment to build closeness with students. In social role theory, teachers act as figures or role models, so the teacher's appearance and form of expression are part of a strategy to get closer to students [5]. The friendly expression displayed by teachers makes them more confident in their daily activities.

The choice of hijab style and model is not only a complement to fulfilling sharia obligations, but can be a tool to convey messages about politeness, firmness of Islamic values, and openness to the development of the times [3, 10]. In the theory of social emotional expression, it is explained that self-confidence can motivate someone to display a friendly and open facial expression to the [5]. From the results of observations conducted by researchers found that fashionable hijab styles make female teachers smile more easily, greet, and have a happier mood. A hijab style that is harmonious and suitable for the shape of the face makes female teachers at SMK Muhammadiyah 1 Kepanjen feel like they appear at their best in the school environment, while still maintaining the values of politeness and professionalism.

C. Relevant to Students

The female teachers at Muhammadiyah 1 Vocational School in Kepanjen realize that most of their students are active TikTok users, making them familiar with popular fashion trends. They feel more connected and relevant to their students' world by following the latest hijab styles appearing on TikTok [1, 3]. Teachers can build closeness with students through emerging trends on social media, especially TikTok [7]. Students will be more open and feel closer to their teachers because they think that teachers understand their world [14].

An attractive and recognizable appearance by students can build emotional closeness, as well as remind female students to always pay attention to the time and place when wearing their clothes [9, 15]. It can be concluded that there is a shift in the meaning of the hijab symbol, where the meaning of the hijab is not only a religious identity, but also as a social bridge between teachers and students. Thus, this trend illustrates a new dynamic, where teachers not only play a role as subject instructors, but also build strong emotional and cultural relationships with students.

D. Content Tik Tok Hijab Tutorials

The hijab style chosen by female teachers at SMK Muhammadiyah 1 Kepanjen is trending towards fashionable hijab while maintaining Islamic values. Fashionable refers to the choice of harmonious colors, neat styles and shapes, and loose clothing that covers the genitals [12, 14]. The female teachers are aware that they are educators who teach in an Islamic school environment, so the clothing they wear must be modest and cover the genitals. Covering the genitals means not revealing the curves of the body and exposing body parts that must be covered according to Islamic law [12, 15].

Looking fashionable does not mean eliminating Islamic values, but can also balance them with aesthetic and ethical values [9, 10]. Female teachers at Muhammadiyah 1 Vocational School, Kepanjen, try to look fashionable by following hijab tutorial trends on TikTok, such as instant square ceruti, pashmina Ceruti, regular square Paris, syar'i headscarf. The hijab model and style are chosen by combining harmony between the top, bottom, and accessories used. With a fashionable and modest appearance, female teachers want to convey the message that wearing the hijab is not only an obligation for women, but also part of a positive spiritual and social expression [12, 15].

Islamic religious education views the hijab trend as part of a da'wah strategy that keeps pace with current developments without diminishing Islamic values [9, 10]. Female teachers want to appear attractive to students and colleagues, while maintaining their spiritual values and role as role models in the school environment. Therefore, a fashionable appearance is permitted as long as it does not violate Islamic law and does not overdo the use of additional accessories.

E. Content Analysis

The results of observations and content analysis obtained from several TikTok accounts followed by female teachers at Muhammadiyah 1 Kepanjen Vocational School are shown in the following table:

TABLE 6.1: Analisis content tutorials

TikTok Account	Content Example	Hijab Styles/Models	Religious Goals and Values
@umnawar	Syar'i hijab tutorial	Pashmina circular, French khimar	Appearing in accordance with Islamic law but still fashionable: practical education
@trenhijab_id	Simple pashmina hijab tutorial	Pashmina inner, oval pashmina	Aesthetic and functional tutorial, adjusting the shape of the face
@alawiyahijab	Simple square hijab tutorial	Instant hijab, elma, chiffon, pashmina	Provides a quick and easy alternative

			and is suitable for everyday and school events
@hijabtutorial.id	Pashmina hijab tutorial	Pashmina tied back	Adapts to the shape of the face and still covers the aurat
@yennisun3	Modern Santi hijab tutorial	Modern santi hijab with elegant accessories	Look beautiful at formal events but still within the limits of Islamic law
@nabilahyosa	Syar'i hijab tutorial	Pashmina hijab, oval hijab	Look elegant but still cover your body
@hijabzidnyofficial	Pashmina hijab tutorial	Instant pashmina hijab, instant hijab	Simple pashmina hijab tutorial that covers the aurat

The data obtained shows that female teachers at SMK Muhammadiyah 1 Kepanjen tend to adapt their hijab styles to the content they follow. The hijab styles and styles adopted from the tutorial content emphasize a fashionable appearance while remaining within the boundaries of Islamic law.

F. Relationship with Islamic Religious Education

In the context of Islamic religious education, female teachers' headscarf styles must adhere to Islamic law. Surah An-Nur, verse 31, explains that wearing a headscarf or hijab must cover the body and reflect modesty, simplicity, and the intention of worship [10, 12]. Islamic religious education teaches proper dress code without separating Islamic values from aesthetics and ethics. Teachers who appear fashionable and polite demonstrate that Islamic values can keep up with the times and are relevant to everyday life. Furthermore, Islamic religious education emphasizes the importance of teachers being role models (uswatun hasanah), moderate (tasawuth), and noble morals (akhlakul karimah) in building self-image in the school environment [14, 15].

A teacher is a figure who serves as a role model for his students, both in their speech, actions, and clothing style. The working principle of a teacher as an educator is emphasized in QS. Al- Ahzab, verse 21, which states that the Prophet Muhammad is a role model (uswatun hasanah) for the people [10, 12]. This principle explains that teachers do not only transfer knowledge, but also become figures who represent the teachings that have been taught. The style and model of hijab of female teachers who follow the hijab trend on TikTok can be an inspiring model of Islamic dress for students, while still upholding the values of modesty and simplicity [7]. Teachers who are able to implement the hijab trend on TikTok while upholding Islamic values, are a form of uswatun hasanah in the era of social media [1].

Sufism or moderation in Islam encourages teachers to adopt a middle ground, that is, not to be extreme or excessive in their dress, especially in wearing the hijab [10]. The concept of moderation in Islam, found in QS. Al-Baqoroh verse 143, encourages Muslims to always maintain balance in living their lives both in this world and the hereafter [10, 12]. This concept encourages female teachers to not appear too glamorous, but also not stiff and shabby. Teachers who appear in hijab styles that follow current developments and do not abandon Islamic values, are actually representing moderation in religious expression [1, 7]. This is a form of cultural da'wah in the school environment, because teachers can be a link between Islamic teachings and the social lives of students who have been influenced by social media.

Morality is the foundation of social expression, encompassing politeness in speech, respect for others, humility, and style of dress [12]. In this case, the hijab trend displayed by female teachers at SMK Muhammadiyah 1 Kepanjen, noble morality is reflected in the way teachers wear fashionable hijabs with a friendly, polite, and modest attitude. Noble morality can be a counterbalance to the potential for excessive adornment due to following hijab trends on social media, especially TikTok [3]. Female teachers at SMK Muhammadiyah 1 Kepanjen realized that hijab style and model are only a means, while morality is the main message.

The three values outlined above provide an important foundation for teachers to express hijab trends adopted on social media. Hijab trends shouldn't be avoided, as long as they don't abandon Islamic values. They can serve as a learning tool, visual preaching, and role model in the school environment. Islamic religious education plays a role in guiding the hijab's meaning, not merely as a covering for the intimate parts of the body but as an expression of holistic Islamic values and character.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study shows that the hijab trend on TikTok adopted by female teachers at SMK Muhammadiyah 1 Kepanjen is not merely a follow-up to a growing trend on social media, but rather an expression of self-identity, social identity, and a visual means of da'wah (Islamic outreach). The various hijab styles and models adopted by female teachers at SMK Muhammadiyah 1 Kepanjen contribute to a sense of confidence during activities. An attractive and recognizable appearance among students can build emotional closeness and remind female students to always pay attention to the time and place when dressing. Appearing fashionable does not mean eliminating Islamic values, but can also balance them with aesthetic and ethical values. The appearance of female teachers who follow the hijab trend on TikTok reflects a friendly and confident expression in the school environment.

In the context of Islamic religious education, the hijab style worn by female teachers must remain in accordance with Islamic law. There are three main values from the perspective of Islamic religious education: *uswatun Hasanah* (good manners), *tawasuth* (religious tolerance), and noble character. The three values outlined above provide an important foundation for teachers to express hijab trends adopted on social media. Islamic religious education plays a role in guiding the interpretation of the hijab, which is not merely a

covering for the private parts, but also an expression of holistic Islamic values and character.

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